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BEFEKTETÉS A JÖVŐBE

Hercules Routes

*Presentation of calculation algorithms,
calculation heuristics and statistics for 2022*

GINOP-2.1.7-15-2016-01364

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1. Abstract

The purpose of this document is to describe the calculation algorithms and the calculation heuristics of the route planning and passenger transport framework system "Hercules Routes", identified as GINOP-2.1.7-15-2016-01364, and presenting the statistics for 2022.

The final result of the development of the Hercules Routes framework is a specific artificial intelligence based on learning algorithms, available as a cloud service through a browser and various applications for companies transporting their employees and for companies contracted to transport their employees. The system, running in the cloud, optimises the resources available (passenger vehicles) to transport workers to and from work in the most efficient way possible (number of people transported, km charge). By choosing the right vehicles and routes, significant cost savings can be achieved on the employer side, on the passenger transport service provider side, and in terms of emissions and noise pollution. Costs can be reduced by choosing the right vehicles for transport and optimising their routes. Transported workers can see up-to-date information on their journeys via a mobile app, and drivers can receive information on the route and the people they are transporting via a driver's mobile or tablet app. All this is combined with a complex in-formatics back-up service that ensures the organisation and punctuality of transport, the information of those involved in the transport of passengers, and the emergency alerts and warnings to be issued in the event of an incident.

For more information, please also read the following document: <https://zenodo.org/record/5804606>

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2. Introduction

Since the emergence of industrial parks in our country, intensive long-distance transport has been developed around industrial parks to cover the needs of commuting to and from work. These long-distance services are, with some exceptions, typically by bus and can cover an area of up to 50-60 km around the industrial estate. Unfortunately, the transport service providers contracting with the factories have no interest in optimising these routes, as they typically contract for fixed-route services, including the distance travelled. Such fixed-route services result in underutilised travel capacity and often half-empty services, imposing unjustified costs on the contracting factories and causing unjustified pollution and noise in the surrounding villages. To make matters worse, the factories located in industrial parks do not group their transport needs together but order them separately from the transport service providers, thus increasing travel costs and burdening the environment.

Focusing on this problem, we aim to implement a service package that optimises long-distance bus services by aggregating the transport needs of industrial parks and then working with contracted transport service providers. Although ready-made software systems for road freight transport have been available for a long time, at the beginning of our work in 2016 there was no solution available on the market for passenger transport, so we decided to develop an R&D-based system of our own design.

From a scientific point of view, the problem is an NP-hard combinatorial optimization problem, a special kind of the famous vehicle routing problem (VRP). Due to the well-known difficulty of the problem, the running time of exact algorithms that give perfect results can take several days or even weeks, and therefore these solutions can only be run on small-scale theoretical problems. In practice, a wide range of approximate algorithms are used instead, such as evolutionary algorithm, particle swarm optimization (PSO), ant colony optimization (ACO), artificial bee colony optimization (ABC), simulated annealing, tabusearch algorithm (TS). Although the runtime of these solutions can be measured in minutes, their major drawback is that the quality of the resulting solution cannot be guaranteed, is not known, and on average they only reach the 95% level (gap = 5%).

The framework we developed is based on artificial intelligence adapted to changing weather and traffic conditions, which is able to predict the average speed of the road sections at any given time, and thus the expected arrival times, from continuously logged GPS data. We formulated the vehicle routing problem as a mixed integer linear programming model to achieve guaranteed quality results. The expected high computational performance was ensured by implementing our own R&D-based heuristics.

Our key requirements for the system were:

- Computational requirements:
 - Complexity: handling up to 500 bus stops and 50 vehicles per industrial park
 - Guaranteed high calculation accuracy: quality $\geq 99\%$, gap $< 1\%$
 - High performance calculation, i.e. short calculation time: $t \leq 90\text{sec}$
- Infrastructure requirements:
 - AI-based self-learning framework
 - Flexible and scalable framework
 - Immediate and complete data delivery
- Expectations:
 - Expected 20% cost reduction through optimisation
 - Reduction of pollution and noise
 - Punctuality, elimination of connecting flights
 - Reduction in administrative time

The development of the "Hercules Routes" framework has resulted in a specialised artificial intelligence based on learning algorithms, available as a cloud service through a browser and various applications for

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companies that transport their employees and for companies contracted to transport their drivers. The system, running in the cloud, optimises the resources available (buses) to transport workers to and from work in the most efficient way possible (number of people transported, km charge). By choosing the right vehicles and routes, significant cost savings can be achieved on the employer side, on the passenger transport service provider side, and in terms of emissions and noise pollution. Costs can be reduced by choosing the right vehicles for transport and optimising their routes. Transported workers can see up-to-date information on their journeys via a mobile app, and drivers can receive information on the route and the people they are transporting via a driver's mobile or tablet app. All this is combined with a complex in-formatics back-up service that ensures the organisation and punctuality of transport, the information of those involved in the transport of passengers, and the emergency alerts and warnings to be issued in the event of an incident.

The purpose of this document is to describe the calculation algorithms and the calculation heuristics of the route planning and passenger transport framework system "Hercules Routes", identified as GINOP-2.1.7-15-2016-01364, and presenting the statistics for 2022.

3. Calculation algorithms

3.1. Calculation process

The initial steps of the calculation are:

- Algorithm type selection: based on the configurations, the algorithm types implemented during the R&D are:
 - Flower petal
 - Waterflow
 - Combinatorial
 - Fixed schedule
 - Implied probability
 - Recursive implication
- Solver type selection: based on configurations, the types of evaluators built in during R&D are:
 - Gurobi
 - CBC
 - LP
 - MS
- System parameter reading.
- Plan aggregation: the purpose of which is to aggregate the demands of the recurring schedules expected according to the recurring workdays into so-called weekly plan demands, in order to make the calculations sufficient to be performed only once per shift.

3-1. figure: Calculation process

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The calculation steps in the evaluation process are iterative and multi-stage, with each iteration level as follows:

- Shift schedule-based parallelisation: which, depending on the configuration, can be e.g.:
 - In case of three shifts, 6:00, 14:00, 22:00 hours schedule,
 - In case of two shifts, 6:00, 18:00 hours schedule.
- Repetition of implementation per spoke: in order to reduce the number of combinations, the route network can be radially subdivided along natural features (rivers without bridges or mountain ranges impassable for buses or less important transfer points). This type of subdivision is called spoke splitting or spoke heuristics. Accordingly, there is a so-called "spoke" implementation of the above algorithms, which performs the computation in parts, and a so-called "disk" implementation, which performs the computation in one step, which can be set in the computation methods configuration. When the disk type algorithm is selected, the execution in a spoke is naturally interpreted as an execution in a single step.
- Iteration on the iterator configuration: when performing calculations, it may happen that the total bus capacity demand - configured with exclusions - or the time limit set for running buses is not sufficient to serve the planned demands, so the result of a calculation may either succeed or fail. However, the rigid output of the calculation can be made flexible by introducing the so-called iterator configuration. Using the iterator configuration, the number of calculation levels can be specified and the percentage increase of each level compared to the default settings can be configured:
 - The spare capacity of the buses,
 - The bus journey time limit,
 - The levels of exclusions.
- Calculating both directions on a single spoke: the significant computational capacity requirement can be further reduced by splitting the calculation into directions, i.e. calculating the directions to work and home on separate threads. In this case, of course, it will be necessary to merge the results obtained in this way according to the "Direction decomposition" heuristic. Whether the calculations are run with or without directional splitting can be configured in the system parameters.

The next phase is the generation of descriptive systems of equations for the algorithm implementation as follows:

- Generate station descriptor equations to ensure that all passengers waiting at a given station are transported.
- Generate vehicle descriptor equations that do not allow more passengers to board a bus than the allowed capacity.
- Generate probability descriptor equations to determine the probability of departure of a bus.

The next phase is the generation of descriptive equation systems for the route network implementation:

- Generate equations describing the route network, which aims to define the route network traversal according to graph-theoretic rules.
- Generation of graph-theoretic heuristic equations to improve the performance of the evaluation engine. Their use can significantly reduce the number of access combinations and running time.
- Generation of exclusion equations to restrict certain vehicle route-station or vehicle route-edge combinations based on exclusion definitions.

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- Generation of a cost description equation to aggregate the cost factors of the transport per bus and to produce the cost function to be optimised.
- Generation of time limit equations, where the available running time is limited for each bus.

The next step is the multithreaded evaluation of the generated equation systems. This requires, however, that the previously generated route network patterns described above are read and used in the evaluation.

After the equations have been evaluated, the next step is to draw up the bus schedule, which consists of the following steps:

- Route planning: the aim is to arrange the set of stations to be visited in an optimal order for each vehicle, based on the calculations. Route planning is only necessary at stations where the onward journey can be made in several directions.
- Use of GPS-based learning speeds and arrival times: the aim is to use a neural network model to generate predicted data from GPS data (vehicle identification, route network edge identification, weather plan data (snow, rain, fog, wind, ice), traffic intensity, direction of travel, day of work, periodic dates (day of the week, day of the month, month of the year), speeds measured from GPS data) and use them to build a bus schedule that approximates reality as closely as possible. The forecast data are as follows:
 - Predicted average speeds per route network edge per vehicle,
 - Predicted arrival times per route network station per vehicle.
- Accounting of calculation results: the aim is to save the resulting schedules, carrier and factory financial data.

After the evaluation of the parallel calculations on the way to work and on the way home, the results are combined according to the "Direction decomposition" heuristic, which we have already described above.

The final step of the evaluation is to replicate the calculation results of the aggregated demands into weekly plans to the initial demands.

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3.2. Algorithm types

The algorithm types implemented during the R&D are:

Name	Description
Flower petal	An algorithm that breaks down the route network computation into parts, similar to plucking flower petals. (deprecated)
Waterflow	An algorithm that performs the route network calculations in a similar way to a flowing water into a valley. (deprecated)
Combinatorial	An algorithm based on the prior generation of feasible combinations that satisfy constraints. (deprecated)
Fixed schedule	An algorithm based on the scheduling of predefined getting on and getting off times. (deprecated)
Implied probability	Complete solution to calculate the structure-based route network. Requires much more computation than previous algorithms.
Recursive implication	Complete solution to compute the loop-based route network. Requires much more computation than previous algorithms.

3-1. figure: Algorithm types

3.3. Solver types

The types of evaluators built in during R&D are:

Name	Description
Gurobi	A product of Gurobi Optimization, LLC.
CBC	A product of COIN-OR Foundation Inc. with Google API
LP	An evaluator from http://lpsolve.sourceforge.net/5.5/
MS	A product of Gurobi Optimization LLC. with limited functionality and Microsoft API

3-2. figure: Solver types

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3.4. Compatibility of algorithm types and solver types

The available algorithm types by solver types are the followings:

Name	Flower petal	Waterflow	Combinatorial	Fixed schedule	Implied probability	Recursive implication
Gurobi	X	X	X	X	X	X
CBC	X	X	X	X	X	X
LP	X	X	X	X		
MS	X	X				

3-3. figure: Compatibility of algorithm types and solver types

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4. Calculation heuristics

4.1. Presence of heuristics

The route network covering the catchment area of industrial parks can be very complex. The combinatorial space required to calculate the optimal result can be as high as 10^{500} combinatorial possibilities in the case of a loop-based model. Heuristics can be used to achieve an acceleration of between 1.5 and 5 times per heuristic, with the aim of boosting the performance of the engine. The heuristic types implemented during the R&D are:

- a) Breaking a problem into parts
 - Spoke decomposition, i.e. splitting into spokes – if the graph to be traversed can be radially divided into parts along natural conditions (a river without a bridge or a mountain range inaccessible to buses, or at less important transfer points), then it is also advisable to run the problem to be optimized by breaking it down into individual subgraphs. This type of division is called splitting into spokes or spoke heuristics. Accordingly, there is also an implementation of the "spoke" that performs the calculations in parts and the so-called "wheel", which performs the calculations in a combined way, which can be set in the body of the calculation methods. Selecting the dial-type algorithm, execution per spoke is naturally interpreted as a one-step execution.
 - Direction decomposition - the task to be optimised usually contains both delivery and return transport requirements, which are evaluated as a combined task to obtain a more efficient but computationally expensive solution. By running the inbound and outbound demands separately and then combining the results using a heuristic, a near-optimal result can be obtained, but with multiple performance gains. Accordingly, there is a so-called "bidirectional" implementation of the algorithms that perform the computations in a "one-way" and in a "two-way", which can be set in the computation methods trunk. By choosing the bi-directional algorithm, the individual directions of the computation are of course performed in a single step.
- b) Graph-theoretic heuristics
 - Adaptive vehicle limitation - the problem to be solved may include central (base) buses in addition to terminal buses, but only those base buses should be included in the prob-scheme calculation that can give a better solution result. Restricting the number of base buses can lead to a multiple increase in performance by applying appropriate heuristics.
 - Graph compression - by default, buses can return anywhere on the upstream or downstream points of an edge of the graph used. However, if this edge of the graph is compressed by a predefined edge length, and buses are only allowed to turn at breakpoints on this edge, then a near-optimal result is obtained, but with a multiple increase in performance.
 - Spanning tree limitation - if we connect the actual pick-up points, drop-off points, vehicle starting point and vehicle incoming point along the shortest paths in all possible combinations per vehicle, we obtain the set of variations of the road sections affected by the problem. The edges outside these road sections will therefore certainly not be affected and need not be taken into account when solving the problem. This heuristic varies depending on the type of problem, and in some cases can result in speedups of up to ten times.

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- Zone limitation
 - Negative zoning - vehicles can be limited in terms of passenger pick-up based on empirical values: no more than an empirical X distance from the shortest road connecting the vehicle to the industrial estate. Along this principle, certain pick-up or drop-off points at impractical distances can be excluded for each vehicle.
 - Positive zoning - demand pick-up or demand delivery points that would be left without a vehicle due to negative zoning, making the task unsolvable. To avoid this, the result of the negative exclusion shall be resolved for the N vehicles closest to them - as a positive correction.
- Graph pattern recognition: artificial intelligence-based recognition and use of recurrent graph features.
- c) Possibility of using "learned starting values"

The evaluation of the problem is much faster when starting the calculation with initial values far from the optimum, but appropriate for the constraints, compared to starting the calculation without initial values. The system provides four heuristics for pre-selecting the appropriate initial values:

 - Incubated start values - the initial values are generated in a self-learning manner, which can result in the actual calculation being accelerated to several times faster.
 - Indicator start values - if the calculation of the incubated initial values exceeds the time frame provided, a useful alternative is to use indicator initial values, where the correct initial values are set by activating the so-called indicator variables in the equation system.
 - Previous solution start values - it may happen that the problem evaluation is a refinement of a previous evaluation of the same problem, with some parameters (e.g. vehicles) constrained, in which case it is useful to use variables fixed from the result of the previous calculation as initial values or constraints.
 - Structure solution start values - the problem to be optimised is generally run on a graph representing a network, but by simplifying the graph into a structure and performing the evaluation on it, the results obtained as initial results can significantly speed up the evaluation of the real network-based problem.
- d) Early interruption of the optimum search
 - Interrupting the search by relative value
 - Interrupting the search by absolute value
 - Interrupting the search with a time limit
 - Interruption by objective function slope: the ratio of the optimum reached to the time spent on optimisation

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4.2. Grouping of heuristics

Heuristics	Breaking a problem into parts	Graph-theoretic heuristics	Learned starting values	Early interruption
Spoke decomposition	X			
Direction decomposition	X			
Adaptive vehicle limitation		X		
Graph compression		X		
Spanning tree limitation		X		
Zone limitation		X		
Graph pattern recognition		X		
Incubated start values			X	
Indicator start values			X	
Previous start values			X	
Structure start values			X	
Interruption by relative value				X
Interruption by absolute value				X
Interruption by objective function slope				X

4-1. figure: Grouping of heuristics

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4.3. Compatibility of algorithm types and heuristics

Heuristics	Flower petal	Waterflow	Combinatorial	Fixed schedule	Implied probability	Recursive implication
Spoke decomposition		X	X		X	X
Direction decomposition		X	X	X	X	X
Adaptive vehicle limitation	X	X	X	X	X	X
Graph compression						X
Spanning tree limitation						X
Zone limitation						X
Graph pattern recognition						X
Incubated start values	X	X	X	X	X	X
Indicator start values			X	X	X	X
Previous start values		X	X	X	X	X
Structure start values						X
Interruption by relative value			X	X	X	X
Interruption by absolute value			X	X	X	X
Interruption by objective function slope			X	X	X	X

4-2. figure: Compatibility of algorithm types and heuristics

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5. Statistics for the year 2022

In this document, the AI base framework was tested over one year period, i.e. from 01.01.2021 to 31.12.2022, according to the following criteria:

- Computational runtime: we expect the majority of cases to be completed within 90 seconds.
- Computational accuracy: we expect the majority of cases to be above 99% accuracy.
- Optimisation impact: measured in terms of distance travelled, fuel and emissions. The pre-optimisation state is the state before the system is implemented, for which we have estimated data. We expect the savings from optimisation to be around 20%.

These statistics have been tested for 5 live sites (industrial parks), the exact names of the sites cannot be disclosed due to lack of consent from the relevant factories or industrial parks.

5.1. Statistics of industrial park “A”

5-1. figure: Industrial park “A” – accuracy of calculation

5-2. figure: Industrial park “A” – runtime of calculation

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Work shifts	Cases	Total distance (Km)		Total consumption (L)		Total CO2 emission (kg)		
		Before opt.	After opt.	Before opt.	After opt.	Before opt.	After opt.	Savings (%)
6:00	301	773 435	367 923	115 612	54 688	306 372	144 923	52,70%
14:00	286	478 214	380 627	72 155	56 871	191 211	150 708	21,18%
22:00	283	415 947	334 798	62 774	50 453	166 350	133 700	19,63%

5-1. table: Industrial park "A" – datas of CO₂ emission

5-3. figure: Industrial park "A" – characteristics of CO₂ emission

5.2. Statistics of industrial park "B"

5-4. figure: Industrial park "B" – accuracy of calculation

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5-5. figure: Industrial park "B" – runtime of calculation

Work shifts	Cases	Total distance (Km)		Total consumption (L)		Total CO ₂ emission (kg)		
		Before opt.	After opt.	Before opt.	After opt.	Before opt.	After opt.	Savings (%)
6:00	343	1 355 565	1 057 254	211 800	155 732	561 269	412 691	26,47%
8:00	240	270 263	177 306	36 383	23 145	96 415	61 333	36,39%
16:00	240	256 040	177 308	34 600	23 145	91 689	61 334	33,11%
18:00	343	1 312 006	1 035 244	205 390	153 499	544 283	406 773	25,26%

5-2. table: Industrial park "B" – datas of CO₂ emission

5-6. figure: Industrial park "B" – characteristics of CO₂ emission

5.3. Statistics of industrial park “C”

5-7. figure: Industrial park “C” – accuracy of calculation

5-8. figure: Industrial park “C” – runtime of calculation

Work shifts	Cases	Total distance (Km)		Total consumption (L)		Total CO2 emission (kg)		Savings (%)
		Before opt.	After opt.	Before opt.	After opt.	Before opt.	After opt.	
6:00	343	521 667	426 448	87 162	63 522	230 980	168 333	27,12%
14:00	339	499 715	375 691	76 170	55 971	201 849	148 323	26,52%
18:00	342	328 997	257 841	37 163	29 740	98 481	78 810	19,97%
22:00	339	484 583	361 048	74 204	53 696	196 640	142 294	27,64%

5-3. table: Industrial park “C” – datas of CO₂ emission

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5-9. figure: Industrial park “C” – characteristics of CO₂ emission

5.4. Statistics of industrial park “D”

5-10. figure: Industrial park “D” – accuracy of calculation

5-11. figure: Industrial park “D” – runtime of calculation

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Work shifts	Cases	Total distance (Km)		Total consumption (L)		Total CO2 emission (kg)		Savings (%)
		Before opt.	After opt.	Before opt.	After opt.	Before opt.	After opt.	
6:00	281	128 951	75 484	14 344	8 811	38 012	23 348	38,58%
14:00	265	139 513	75 249	15 522	8 735	41 133	23 148	43,72%
22:00	239	91 799	65 670	10 509	7 644	27 849	20 255	27,27%

5-4. table: Industrial park "D" – datas of CO₂ emission

5-12. figure: Industrial park "D" – characteristics of CO₂ emission

5.5. Statistics of industrial park "E"

5-13. figure: Industrial park "E" – accuracy of calculation

5-14. figure: Industrial park “E” – runtime of calculation

Work shifts	Cases	Total distance (Km)		Total consumption (L)		Total CO2 emission (kg)		
		Before opt.	After opt.	Before opt.	After opt.	Before opt.	After opt.	Savings (%)
6:00	344	1 145 911	622 636	190 984	100 472	506 108	266 252	47,39%
14:00	332	779 712	608 670	119 462	97 348	316 574	257 972	18,51%
18:00	266	392 065	115 201	40 796	12 275	108 110	32 530	69,91%
22:00	332	865 066	598 502	117 370	95 350	311 030	252 677	18,76%

5-5. table: Industrial park “E” – datas of CO₂ emission

5-15. figure: Industrial park “E” – characteristics of CO₂ emission

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6. Conclusions

In this document, we have reviewed the calculation algorithms and the calculation heuristics of the route planning and passenger transport framework system "Hercules Routes", identified as GINOP-2.1.7-15-2016-01364, and presenting the statistics for 2022.

In developing this framework, the objective was to implement a service package that would optimise long-distance bus services by aggregating the transport needs of industrial parks and then working with contracted transport service providers. By choosing the right vehicles and routes, we hoped to achieve significant cost savings and reduce emissions and noise pollution. In line with this, our key measurable expectations for the system were:

- Guaranteed high calculation accuracy: quality $\geq 99\%$, gap $< 1\%$
- High performance computation, i.e. short computation time: $t \leq 90\text{sec}$
- Expected 20% reduction in cost and environmental impact

These measurable results have been analysed on the basis of statistics from 5 live sites (industrial parks) for the last year, i.e. from 01/01/2021 to 31/12/2022:

- Based on the measured results, we can state that both the accuracy of the calculation results and the calculation time have been met in all cases, and in the case of smaller industrial parks, shorter calculation times and often only 100% quality results were obtained.
- Our expectations for cost reductions were significantly influenced by the followings impacts:
 - Geographic differences: there are differences in the route network of industrial parks due to the natural features of the surroundings of the factories, such as the boundaries of mountains, rivers or the considerable distance from motorways.
 - Changes over time: such as the changes caused by the war in Ukraine, which affected production needs, the number of workers and through them, changes in travel distance.
 - In terms of cost savings per industrial park, we have achieved the expected average savings of 20% in all cases, but for some parks we have exceeded this level by a large margin as a result of mentioned changes.

Overall, our work has been successful and we are confident that the framework will be rolled out to other industrial parks in the hope of a more economical, greener, flexible package of route planning and passenger transport services.

	Hercules Routes:	ID: HR-CA+CH+S
	Presentation of calculation algorithms, calculation heuristics and statistics for 2002	Date: 2022.12.27.
		Rating: public

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